

The Ibero-American Indicators of Sport and Physical Activity for Sustainable Development

Methodology for Evaluating the Quality of the Indicators

Published in 2025 by the Ibero-American Sports Council (Consejo Iberoamericano del Deporte, CID) in collaboration with the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO).

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15191277

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Content

Content.....	3
Methodology for Evaluating the Quality of Ibero-American Sports and Physical Activity Indicators for Sustainable Development	4
A. Evaluation of the Technical Attributes of the Indicators by the Countries.....	5
Clarity	6
Feasibility	7
Relevance.....	8
Cost-effectiveness.....	9
B. Evaluation of the Value Estimation of Indicators and Sources of Information by the Consulting Team.....	10
References	11

Methodology for Evaluating the Quality of Ibero-American Sports and Physical Activity Indicators for Sustainable Development

This document presents the methods used to assess the quality of the Ibero-American indicators of sport and physical activities for sustainable development. It refers to a two-phase framework:

- A. Evaluation of the technical attributes of the indicators by the countries.
- B. Evaluation of the value estimation of indicators and sources of information by the Consortium's consulting team (independent analysts and researchers from King Juan Carlos University).

A. Evaluation of the Technical Attributes of the Indicators by the Countries

The countries participating in the second phase of the study must evaluate the technical attributes of the indicators (1) to ensure that the Ibero-American indicators of sport and physical activity for sustainable development have been understood by the countries; and (2) that the indicators are truly relevant for measuring the potential impact of sport and physical activity for sustainable development.

We provide countries with an indicator evaluation template following the standards of the National Council for the Evaluation of Social Development Policy of Mexico (CONEVAL, 2023). These standards regulate and coordinate the evaluation of the National Social Development Policy and the policies, programs, and actions carried out by public agencies, such as the Federal Programs and Actions for Social Development (CONEVAL, 2024), including those of the National Commission for Social Development, Physical Culture and Sports, which is the sport governing body in Mexico.

The evaluation model presented in our study aligns with that proposed in other reference documents, such as the one prepared by the Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA, 2004), which was used by the Commonwealth (Sherry et al., 2019) in its proposal to evaluate indicators on the role of basic activity and sport in achieving the sustainable development goals. Nonetheless, the use and adaptation of the CONEVAL document to evaluate our proposed indicators has the advantage of being more aligned and appropriate to the context of the Ibero-American region.

Therefore, following CONEVAL (2023), four evaluation criteria were included: one related to a global assessment (clarity) and three more specific criteria (feasibility, cost-effectiveness, and relevance).

As a particular adaptation for this study, a five-point Likert scale was included for each of the criteria-related statements to allow for greater discrimination in the assessment of the indicators. According to Sullivan and Artino (2013), Likert scale responses should be designed to generate interval data, not just ordinal data, to improve subsequent analysis. Considering this, and following Vagias's (2006) recommendations for creating Likert scales, five possible responses with five associated values were included:

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

A numerical score will be calculated for each criterion during the indicator assessment. The following section provides a description of each assessment criterion and the associated statements.

Clarity

An indicator is clear when there is no doubt about what it is intended to measure. That is, the indicator's name is self-explanatory and consistent with the calculation method, and the description of the variables used allows any stakeholder to understand the terms and concepts applied (CONEVAL, 2023, p. 12). Table 1 describes the statements used to evaluate the indicator clarity criterion.

Table 1. *Statements to evaluate the clarity of the indicators*

Statements	Answer and Value	Explanation
The name of the indicator is self-explanatory (it correctly expresses the unit of measurement, does not use acronyms, or defines them precisely).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree 	
The definition of the indicator is consistent with its name.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree 	
The definition of the indicator is consistent with its calculation formula.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree 	
The units of measurement of the variables in the indicator's calculation formula are consistent.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree 	

Feasibility

An indicator is considered as feasible when the calculation method and the sources of information are such that the indicator can be effectively evaluated with the available human, financial, material, and information resources, among others (CONEVAL, 2023, p. 17). In this case, it refers to the resources available to the national sports governing body or the members of the government involved in the calculation of the indicators; or, in the absence of such resources, that the effort required for their evaluation does not represent an extraordinary burden. Table 2 shows the statements for evaluating the feasibility criterion for indicators.

Table 2. Statements to evaluate the feasibility of the indicators

Statements	Answer and Value	Explanation
Currently, the sources of information for calculating the indicator are available from the national sports governing body or official government sources.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree 	
If the sources of information for calculating the indicator are not currently available from the national sports governing body or official government sources, it would be possible to generate them without requiring extraordinary human or material resources from the government.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree 	

Relevance

An indicator is relevant when it provides effective information about a higher-order theme (CONEVAL, 2023, p. 17) linked to strategic objectives of policies for sport and/or physical activities. For example, the indicator is relevant if it provides information on gender gaps in sports practice, as one of the objectives of sports policy is specifically to reduce gender gaps in access to sport and physical activities. Table 3 shows the statement for evaluating the relevance criterion for indicators.

Table 3. *Statement for the Evaluation of the Relevance of the Indicators*

Statement	Answer and Value	Explanation
The indicator addresses a higher-order theme related to the objectives of sports and/or physical activity policies or programs.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree 	

Cost-effectiveness

An indicator is considered cost-effective if the benefit of generating the information exceeds the economic or human costs required to calculate it. It is also appropriate to compare the cost of generating the indicator with the annual budget of the national sports governing body (CONEVAL, 2023, p. 17). Table 4 presents the criteria for evaluating the cost-effectiveness of indicators.

Table 4. *Statement for evaluating the cost-effectiveness of indicators*

Statement	Answer and Value	Explanation
The usefulness of the indicator in measuring the contribution of sport, physical education, or exercise to achieving a sustainable development goal justifies the cost or effort associated with its calculation.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither agree nor disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree 	

B. Evaluation of the Value Estimation of Indicators and Sources of Information by the Consulting Team

To evaluate the estimation of the value of each indicator and the sources of information used for that purpose, online Excel files will be made available to the countries. In these files, the Consortium's consulting team (analysts and researchers from the King Juan Carlos University) will validate and provide feedback on the data generated by the countries. The completion of these files will serve as the basis for preparing the technical sheets for the indicators and for maintaining a detailed record of the review and validation process of the information provided by the countries.

The Consortium's consulting team will determine whether the data obtained by the countries corresponds to that contained in the documents provided as sources of information and whether these are official sources that meet international technical standards. The assessment conducted by the consulting team is aligned with the recommendations on statistical results provided by the European Statistical System (2019) regarding the principles of relevance, accuracy and reliability, consistency, comparability, and accessibility. Additionally, the consulting team will verify that the estimation of the indicators' values corresponds to the guidelines for the technical specifications for each indicator.

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